

Application`s Aspects Of Public Relations By Nonprofit Organizations. Case Study Albania

Xhiliola Agaraj(Shehu)¹, Merita Murati², Valbona Gjini³

Abstract—The traditional *public relations manager* is usually responsible for maintaining and enhancing the reputation of the organization among key publics. While the principal focus of this effort is on support publics, it is quite clearly recognized that an organization's image has important effects on its own employees, its donors and volunteers, and its clients.

The aim of paper is to define application`s aspects of public relations media and tools by nonprofit organizations in Albanian reality. Actually does used public relations media and tools, like written material, audiovisual material, organizational identity media, news, interviews and speeches, events, web sites by nonprofit organizations to attract donors? If, public relations media and tools are used, does exists a relation between public relation media and fundraising?

Keywords—Donors, Fundraising, Nonprofit Organizations, Public Relations

I. INTRODUCTION

TRADITIONAL public relations are often confused with one of its sub functions, such as press agency, company publications, lobbying, fire fighting, and so forth. Yet it is a more inclusive concept. The most frequently quoted definition of PR is the following:

Public relations are the management function that evaluates the attitudes of important publics, identifies the policies and procedures of an individual or an organization with the public interest, and executes a program of action to earn understanding and acceptance by these publics.

The public relations function can be accorded high or low influence in the organization, depending on the board's and chief executive officer's attitude toward the function. In some organizations, the public relations manager is a vice president and sits in on all meetings involving information and actions that might affect public perceptions of the organization. He or she not only puts out fires but also counsels management on actions that will avoid starting fires. In other organizations, public relations are a middle management function charged with getting out publications and handling news and special events. The public relations people are not involved in policy or strategy formulation, only in tactics.

By employing a public relations manager, the organization can gain several advantages: (1) better anticipation of potential

problems, (2) consistent public-oriented policies and strategies, and (3) more professional written and oral communications.organization must have to concentrate more of its attention on some publics than others. A nonprofit organization has primary, secondary and tertiary publics.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

The emergence of marketing as a "hot topic" in nonprofit circles has raised a major question in the minds of chief administrators and public relations managers as to the relationship between marketing and public relations in a nonprofit organization. Clearly, the two functions work well together in business firms with marketing focusing on the development of plans to market the company's products to consumers, while public relations takes care of relations with other publics. In nonprofit organizations, however, the relationship between the public relations and marketing departments has often been marked by tension and lack of clearly defined areas of responsibility.

We see the following differences between public relations and marketing:

- Public relations are primarily a communication tool, whereas marketing also includes other elements of the marketing mix.
- Public relations seek to influence awareness and attitudes, whereas marketing tries to influence specific behaviors, such as purchasing, joining, voting, donating, and so on.
- Public relations do not define the goals of the organization, whereas marketing is intimately involved in defining the business's mission, target audiences, positioning, and interventions.

Nonprofit organizations would like to have good relations with every public that is affected by, or affects it. An

An organization's primary publics are those that it relates to actively and continuously, such as clients, employees, directors, and the general community. Secondary publics are those it must monitor and relate to less frequently but on a fairly continuous basis-suppliers, agents, government officials, and competitors. Tertiary groups are those that do not have any present impact on the organization but whose support and goodwill may be helpful in the future. Tertiary publics may also include groups to whom the organization might like to market in the future.

There are some public relations tools that influence target public and nonprofit organizations objectives.

Written materials: Organizations rely extensively on written

¹ Ph.D. Xhiliola Agaraj (Shehu), Department of Business, University of Vlora, Albania, email: xhiliagaraj@yahoo.com

² Ph.D student Merita Murati, Specialist at Chamber Commerce, e-mail: meri_murati@yahoo.com

³ Ph.D Student Valbona Gjini, Department of Finance, University of Vlora, Albania, e-mail: v_gjini@yahoo.com

materials to communicate with their target publics, such as annual reports, catalogues, employee newsletters, informational flyers, and posters.

Audiovisual materials: such as films, slides, CD are coming into increasing use as communication tools.

Organization Identity Media: Normally, an organization's various visual and print materials lack a uniform look, which not only creates confusion but also misses an opportunity to create and reinforce an *organization identity* or *brand*. In an over communicated society, organizations compete for attention. The objective is to create a visual identity that the public immediately recognizes. Visual identity is conveyed through logos, Web sites, brochures, signs, business forms, buildings, uniforms.

News: One of the major tasks of a public relations department is to find or create favorable news about the organization and market it to the appropriate media. As someone once said, "Publicity is sent to a medium and *prayed for* while advertising is sent to a medium and *paid for*." Publicity is far from free, however, because special skills are required to write good publicity and to "reach" the press. Good publicists cost money. Publicity has three qualities that make it a worthwhile investment. First, it may have *higher veracity* than advertising because it appears as normal news and not as sponsored information. Second, it tends to catch people off guard who might otherwise avoid sponsored messages. Third, it has high potential for dramatization in that it arouses attention, coming as it does in the guise of a noteworthy event.

Events: One of the major tasks of a public relations department is to find or create favorable news about the organization and market it to the appropriate media. So a nonprofit organization to attract attention of target publics can organize research symposia, celebrate anniversaries of important events in the history of institution, hold news conferences etc.

Interviews and Speeches: Increasingly effective vehicles for publicity are the media interview, Web "chat rooms" and the TV and radio talk shows.

The Web Site: In the new millennium, an extremely important source of information and insight about the nonprofit

organization is its Web site. Web sites can present facts about the organization, recent press releases, examples of advertisements and programs, all designed to give visitors a sense of the organizations and what they do. Web sites are places where one can learn about crises. They are places where one can go to volunteer or to donate. If they are well designed, they will have ways for visitors to follow up with personal contacts. There will be links to other sites visitors might find helpful and perhaps chat rooms where they can "meet" and discuss common concerns.

III. METHODOLOGY OF RESEARCH

With the purpose of research, were used three methodological research instruments: questionnaires, focus groups and depth interviews. The questionnaire was designed such as to identify the involvement of elements of marketing in nonprofit organizations, their importance, the identification of various donors and the use of marketing elements in the provision of funds. Intense interviews and focus groups aimed at providing a more detailed information on the questions asked. Depth interviews and focus groups were conducted after processing the questionnaire in order to argument the findings of its own non-profit organizations (NPO). Discussion topics in the argument consisted of using the elements of marketing by nonprofit organizations to reach their target audience, and in particular donors. For the selection of samples was used database available at Tirana District Court on the registration of all NPOs in Albania. The object of study would be nonprofit organizations that exercise their activity in Tirana, in the North and South of Albania. The sample was extracted and a random selection was made based on percentages of NPOs according to their type, enabling the reflection of the respective percentages. And of 82 selected NPOs, 51.8% are associations, 11.7% are foundations and 37.8% are centers. The data obtained through the questionnaire were processed through a computer program SPSS (Statistical Package for Social Sciences). During analysis were used control procedures to ensure their reliability.

IV. DATA ANALYSES AND FINDING PRESENTATION

Fig 1 Assessment of usage of written materials to communicate with public

Among written material, monthly, quarterly, average from 4,76, (1 min, 5 max). 86.6% of nonprofit anniversary reports have a high usage, and characterized by an

organization surveyed, declare that edition of reports are frequently.

Brochures are used with a usage level from 4.33, where 66.7% of nonprofit organizations surveyed declare that those have a high usage.

Books like a tool of written materials are characterized by an average use, while news and magazines are little used. 21.3% of NPO's declare that books have a high level of use, and this is distinctive of NPO's that are more active, that means, that are involved in some projects. (Fig 1)

TABLE I
 ASSESSMENT OF USE OF WRITTEN MATERIALS BY TYPE OF NPO'S

Assessment of usage of written material	Min	Max	Asociation	Foundation	Center
Assessment of usage of report	1	5	4.69	5.00	4.84
Assessment of usage of newspapers	1	5	2.88	3.11	2.26
Assessment of usage of brochures	1	5	4.14	4.56	4.77
Assessment of usage of magazines	1	5	2.31	2.67	2.71
Assessment of usage of books	1	5	2.93	3.67	3.46

Table I exhibit the level of use of written materials by type of NPO's, where monthly, quarterly, and anniversary reports have a high level of usage by association, foundation, and centers, because 90 % of NPO's in Albania are financing by international donators, and this is one of their criterions, which, all NPO's are practicing.

Newspapers have an average level of usage, but are little used by centers. Brochures are used by association, and are used a lot of by foundations and centers. Magazines and books have an average level of usage.

TABLE II
 ASSESSMENT OF USE OF WRITTEN MATERIALS BY LOCATION OF NPO'S

Assessment of usage of written material	Min	Max	Tirana	North	South
Assessment of usage of report	1	5	4.72	4.83	4.84
Assessment of usage of newspapers	1	5	3.18	1.96	2.53
Assessment of usage of brochures	1	5	4.56	4.13	4.53
Assessment of usage of magazines	1	5	3.00	2.13	1.95
Assessment of usage of books	1	5	3.65	2.74	2.80

Table II exhibits, the level of usage of written materials by location. By the table conclude that anniversary reports have a high level of use regardless location. Newspapers have a moderately use in centre of Albania and are little used at north and south of Albania. This is related with the activity of

NPO's, which are a little active at north and south of Albania. Magazines have an moderately use at north of Albania and little used at south, while books are used more at centre of Albania (Tirana) and little used at north and south.

Fig 2 Assessment of use of audiovisual materials by NPO's

Among audiovisual materials a large usage have slides, which are used to present results of a project or a study in a scientific conference, or to clients, or in meetings that organized between NPO's. A consideration part of NPO's use photos (4.07), the aim is to be transparent in project implementation

in relation to donors and clients. Films have a level of use above average (3.84), because considered expensive by NPO's in relation with benefits. CD's have an average usage, and 48.1% declare that are not used.

TABLE III
 ASSESSMENT OF USE OF AUDIOVISUAL MATERIALS BY TYPE OF NPO'S

Assessment of usage of audiovisual material	Min	Max	Association	Foundation	Center
Assessment of usage of films	1	5	3.64	4.22	4.00
Assessment of usage of slides	2	5	4.48	4.67	4.32
Assessment of usage of CD's	1	5	2.67	2.56	3.13
Assessment of usage of photos	1	5	3.89	4.00	4.18

If looked the level of use of audiovisual materials by type of NPO's, conclude that the level of use is common regardless type of NPO's. Films, slides, photos are used regardless type

of NPO's, while CD's have an moderately use for all types of NPO's.

TABLE IV
 ASSESSMENT OF USE OF AUDIOVISUAL MATERIALS BY LOCATION OF NPO'S

Assessment of usage of audiovisual material	Min	Max	Tirana	North	South
Assessment of usage of films	1	5	4.0	3.79	3.58
Assessment of usage of slides	2	5	4.9	4.67	4.05
Assessment of usage of CD's	1	5	2.9	2.92	2.58
Assessment of usage of photos	1	5	3.2	3.78	4.27

If looked the level of use of audiovisual materials by locations, the level of use is common, regardless locations.

Films, slides, photos are used by three regions surveyed, while CD's have an average usage.

Fig. 3 Assessment of use of public relations by NPO's

59% of NPO`s surveyed have a web site, through which the public can take information, and 41% of them haven`t a web site. The part of NPO`s that haven`t web site are not more active, or if they are don`t want to consume because don`t look more effective. Web site as a tool of public relations is characterized by an average from 3.63 that means it is up to average. Events, interviews, news, identity media are used with an average from 3.5. If is looked the level of use of public relations by type of NPO`s, those have a level up to average, regardless type of NPO`s. The reasons are:

- Are more Credible
- Are little expensive.

The level of use of public relations by NPO`s that operate in Tirana city is higher, compare with NPO`s that

operate in two other region of Albania. One of the tools of public relations that have a significant difference in relation with level of use is web site, which has a high level of use in Tirana and an average level of use at north and south of Albania. This fact evidence that NPO`s that operate in center of Albania (Tirana) are more active than NPO`s that operate at north and south.

TABLE V
 ASSESSMENT OF USE OF PUBLIC RELATIONS TO ATTRACT DONORS

Assessment of usage of public relations	Government	Individual donators	Private Businesses	Foundations	International donors
Assessment of usage of written material	3.91	4.00	3.90	3.93	3.91
Assessment of usage of audiovisual material	4.06	4.00	4.10	4.07	4.04
Assessment of usage of identity media	3.34	3.71	3.52	3.74	3.47
Assessment of usage of news	3.76	4.14	3.95	4.07	3.70
Assessment of usage of interviews	3.85	4.29	4.00	4.24	3.82
Assessment of usage of events	3.52	4.29	3.76	4.07	3.58
Assessment of usage of web site	3.30	3.29	3.43	3.46	3.65

Public relations media are used by NPO`s to obtain funds from government, individual donations, private businesses, foundations, and international donators.

The level of use of public relations to attract donors is up to average, while web site have a moderately use, compare with other tools.

TABLE VI
 STATISTICAL SIGNIFICANCE BETWEEN PUBLIC RELATION AND FUNDRAISING

Assessment of correlation between public relations and fundraising through Che Squire test	Government	Individual donators	Businesses	Foundations	International donors
Assessment of usage of written material	.929	.199	.992	.501	.739
Assessment of usage of audiovisual material	.239	.945	.883	.357	.279
Assessment of usage of identity media	.784	.130	.928	.073	.228
Assessment of usage of news	.251	.306	.379	.003	.177
Assessment of usage of interviews	.536	.208	.576	.003	.008
Assessment of usage of events	.816	.049	.524	.008	.000
Assessment of usage of web site	.245	.159	.787	.293	.006

The table VI show the statistical significance of link between public relations tools and fundraising. The link between public relations and fundraising has statistical significance because:

- The correlation between level of use of news and fundraising from foundation has statistical significance.
- The correlation between level of use of interviews, news conferences and fundraising from foundation and international donators has statistical significance.
- The correlation between the level of use of events and fundraising from individual donators, international donators has statistical significance.

The square test for each public relations tools mention above is fewer than reliability level 0.05. This means that hypothesis Ho "there is no correlation between public relation and fundraising" fall down. Public relations tools are used by NPO's because aren't expensive, and are more credible.

V. CONCLUSIONS

Written materials as one of the public relations tools that are used to communicate with public, and to attract donors have a moderately use. Are more used anniversary reports, and have a high level of use brochures, while magazines, newspapers or

REFERENCES

- [1] Adrian Sargeant "Marketing management for nonprofit organization". 2005 pp 30-44
- [2] Albert Bandura : "Self Efficacy: Toward a Unifying Theory of Behavior Change" 1997, Vol 84, pp1991-215
- [3] Arnold, M.J., & Yapp,S.R "Direct Marketig in nonprofit services" Journal of services Marketing, 2003 pp141 160
- [4] Philip Kotler, AlanR.Andreassen "Strategic marketing for nonprofit organizations". 2003 pp 442-480
- [5] Philip Kotler and Sidney J.Levy "Broadning the Concept of Marketing" 1969,pp 10-15

books have an average level of use. Are fewer used magazines, newspapers, and books by NPO's that operate at north and south of Albania, one of the reasons is that NPO's that operate at this region are fewer active. Audiovisual materials to communicate with public are used, because those are no expensive. The level of use of slides is high, photos, films, and CD's have a moderately level of use. The level of use of audiovisual materials by type, and location of NPO's is common. The level of use of public relations tools to communicate with public is up to average for most of them and are more used written and audiovisual materials. The reason is those are credible and not expensive. If is looked the level of use by location conclude that north and south of Albania have an average level of use of web site, compare with center of Albania which is in a high level. Public relations tools must have to be a high level of use, since are not expensive and credible. Among public relations tools which are more credible are those that are manage from a third person. To have more transparence, and more information above projects, and to increase credibility all communication tools must used more.

- [6] Philip Kotler and Gerard Zaltman, "Social Marketing" Journal of Marketing 1971, pp3-12
- [7] Philip Kotler, Alan R.Andreassen "Strategic marketing for nonprofit organizations". 2003 pp 190-97
- [8] Kline Henley.T "Integrated marketing communication for local nonprofit organization: Communication tool and Method". Journal of Nonprofit & Public Sector marketing 2001 pp 157-168
- [9] Kline Henly, T. "Integrated marketing communication for local nonprofit organization: Developing an integrated marketing communication strategy:. Journal of nonprofit & Public Sector Marketing, 2001 pp 141-155
- [10] Walter W. Wymer, "Nonprofit and Business Sector Collaboration" 2003 pp23